

Voices of Learning: Generating Culturally Relevant Educational Podcasts with AI

AUTHORS SECTION

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ABSTRACT

Generative artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionize education by transforming text-based content into more engaging and accessible learning experiences, such as podcasts. However, many existing AI-generated educational tools lack cultural relevance, limiting their effectiveness for diverse student populations. This proposed project aims to enhance AI-generated educational podcasts by fine-tuning both script generation and voice models to better reflect a wider range of cultural perspectives. By incorporating diverse vernaculars, particularly from Black creators, and collaborating with students from underrepresented communities, this project seeks to improve engagement and student perception. Through these efforts, the project aims to create more inclusive and personalized learning experiences that better resonate with a broad range of learners.

KEYWORDS

artificial intelligence in education; personalized learning; content transformation

INTRODUCTION

Generative artificial intelligence (AI) is reshaping education, offering new ways to enhance student engagement and learning. One promising application is AI-generated educational podcasts, as seen in consumer products like NotebookLM, which allows users to upload materials and generate AI-narrated content. Do et al. (2024) introduced PAIGE, a system that uses large language models (LLMs) to generate personalized educational podcasts from textbook chapters. Their findings showed that students not only learned effectively but also found the experience more engaging than reading, making it a valuable study tool. However, PAIGE relied on proprietary off-the-shelf models, particularly Gemini, without fine-tuning for cultural relevance, and their personalization did not account for students' cultural backgrounds. Since most LLMs are developed in the West, they often struggle to capture diverse cultural perspectives, which can introduce biases and limit their ability to provide truly personalized learning experiences (Blanchard & Mohammed, 2024).

Research on voice recognition shows that marginalized linguistic features are often underrepresented or misidentified, highlighting the need for more equitable design (Bajorek, 2019; Chen et al., 2022; Martin & Wright, 2023). Our project addresses these gaps by refining AI-generated podcasts for cultural relevance through diverse scripts and broader voice libraries. By fine-tuning pre-trained models with domain-specific data, we embed cultural authenticity into AI-generated content. Research further indicates that students who see themselves reflected in learning materials report stronger motivation (Edouard, 2024a; Edouard & Stewart, 2024). Integrating culturally responsive pedagogy counters the erasure of non-dominant voices (Edouard, 2024b), and evidence suggests that inclusive design fosters deeper student connections, mitigates stereotypes, and encourages narrative sharing (Edouard & Stewart, 2024). As generative AI continues to advance, ensuring it captures the full range of student experiences is critical for equitable, impactful education.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

This project seeks to address existing gaps by fine-tuning both script and voice generation models for cultural relevance in collaboration with students. To improve script generation, we will fine-tune an open-source LLM, such as DeepSeek (Liu et al., 2025), using podcast scripts that reflect a broad range of speech patterns, while collaborating with students to create a truly personalized system that reflects their culture and preferences. By incorporating vernaculars, accents, and cultural perspectives from Black students, the project will investigate how student-designed AI podcasters, customized to reflect their identities, can influence engagement, self-efficacy, metacognition, and learning outcomes through a series of mixed-methods studies.

Through co-design and iterative testing with students, the project will also develop practical guidelines for creating inclusive, culturally relevant AI-generated learning experiences. By centering student voices and identities in the design of AI podcasters, the project will explore how representation influences learners' engagement, sense of belonging, and perceptions of educational content. These insights will deepen our understanding of how large language models can be used to support equity in education. To ensure broader impact, the project will also release an open-source pipeline for creating personalized, identity-aligned AI podcasts, enabling educators and researchers to build on this work in diverse learning environments.

GENERATIVE AI USE

We employed generative AI at the sentence level (e.g., fixing grammar, re-wording sentences). We evaluated the output by proofreading. The authors assume all responsibility for the content of this submission.

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